

1 Supplementary Information - Appendices

2 Appendix A: Reference values lookup tables

3 **Table A1:** Lookup values for condition indicator scaling - Forest ecosystems. Units: AGB
4 (Mg/Ha), SOC (Mg/Ha), EV (mm/yr), TBP (kg/Ha).

ID	AGB		SOC		EV 2010		EV 2020		TBP 2010		TBP 2020	
	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX
211	0.00	0.88	0.00	1.05	0.24	0.43	0.12	0.43	13.24	134.93	17.62	63.69
212	0.00	1.08	0.00	1.71	0.16	0.43	0.10	0.43	19.07	177.40	20.65	77.66
213	0.00	1.04	0.00	0.99	0.23	0.43	0.17	0.43	54.35	163.58	24.33	71.48
221	0.00	1.07	0.00	0.76	0.11	0.43	0.05	0.43	29.09	130.59	17.51	68.00
222	0.00	1.12	0.00	1.11	0.12	0.43	0.07	0.43	27.97	163.86	16.53	74.66
223	0.00	1.09	0.00	1.17	0.14	0.43	0.08	0.43	54.20	181.34	22.68	80.53
231	0.00	1.07	0.00	0.96	0.10	0.43	0.06	0.43	45.45	125.22	19.04	66.41
232	0.00	1.08	0.00	0.87	0.09	0.43	0.04	0.43	20.17	150.44	26.98	81.18
233	0.00	1.12	0.00	1.45	0.12	0.43	0.05	0.43	1.65	172.58	0.24	81.67
241	0.00	1.01	0.01	0.74	0.09	0.43	0.06	0.30	68.40	105.61	35.58	61.98
242	0.00	1.02	0.00	1.05	0.08	0.43	0.03	0.43	26.35	153.86	11.14	81.13
243	0.00	1.13	0.00	1.53	0.12	0.43	0.03	0.43	0.00	168.51	0.00	81.95
251	0.00	1.07	0.05	1.02	0.09	0.43	0.06	0.43	56.48	120.54	23.47	65.87
252	0.00	1.11	0.03	1.25	0.06	0.43	0.03	0.43	55.33	156.58	35.02	81.13
253	0.00	1.11	0.13	1.48	0.09	0.43	0.05	0.43	51.76	176.09	32.19	80.92

5

6 **Table S2:** Lookup values for condition indicator scaling - Agricultural ecosystems. Units:
7 AGB (Mg/Ha), SOC (Mg/Ha), EV (mm/yr), TBP (kg/Ha).

ID	AGB		SOC		EV 2010		EV 2020		TBP 2010		TBP 2020	
	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX
411	0.00	0.80	0.00	1.24	0.16	0.54	0.10	0.53	19.46	140.18	22.67	57.33
412	0.00	0.99	0.00	1.06	0.16	0.48	0.09	0.49	18.05	159.13	20.52	62.78
413	0.00	0.98	0.00	0.88	0.19	0.49	0.13	0.53	43.95	139.06	19.84	70.26
421	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.07	0.12	0.50	0.05	0.51	16.70	137.68	11.55	62.90
422	0.00	1.13	0.00	1.25	0.11	0.51	0.05	0.49	36.50	143.10	22.80	69.13
423	0.00	1.05	0.00	0.91	0.16	0.47	0.10	0.48	21.31	172.95	19.65	70.77
431	0.00	0.86	0.00	0.72	0.09	0.42	0.06	0.38	25.90	123.71	21.26	62.75
432	0.00	0.90	0.00	0.83	0.11	0.51	0.05	0.49	14.61	137.86	17.38	71.42
433	0.00	1.10	0.00	0.99	0.17	0.51	0.08	0.51	29.23	158.77	17.98	70.32
441	0.00	0.71	0.00	0.46	0.11	0.28	0.06	0.20	56.86	91.54	40.80	48.69
442	0.00	0.77	0.00	1.01	0.09	0.39	0.08	0.37	25.61	131.58	18.48	69.72
443	0.00	1.04	0.00	1.22	0.12	0.54	0.05	0.51	2.06	159.32	0.30	74.62
451	0.00	0.33	0.21	0.59	0.15	0.27	0.09	0.22	57.26	97.58	29.90	47.80
452	0.00	0.69	0.13	0.84	0.17	0.39	0.11	0.28	66.53	121.26	32.46	55.46

453 0.00 0.98 0.29 0.90 0.21 0.46 0.11 0.38 54.68 163.11 34.76 61.79

8

9 **Table S3:** Lookup values for condition indicator scaling - Urban and industrial
10 ecosystems. Units: AGB (Mg/Ha), SOC (Mg/Ha), EV (mm/yr), TBP (kg/Ha).

ID	AGB		SOC		EV 2010		EV 2020		TBP 2010		TBP 2020	
	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX
511	0.00	0.55	0.00	1.10	0.22	0.55	0.14	0.59	0.03	137.43	2.95	57.83
512	0.00	0.53	0.00	1.51	0.15	0.53	0.11	0.53	0.00	145.38	10.88	65.24
513	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.99	0.18	0.49	0.12	0.53	45.30	142.18	24.48	65.43
521	0.00	0.70	0.00	0.93	0.12	0.55	0.06	0.59	1.23	135.71	1.26	60.68
522	0.00	0.59	0.00	1.01	0.14	0.54	0.05	0.49	10.00	131.31	3.06	68.60
523	0.00	0.63	0.00	0.98	0.16	0.48	0.12	0.48	31.38	135.32	16.15	71.29
531	0.00	0.65	0.00	0.56	0.11	0.34	0.06	0.36	22.48	125.17	15.34	56.71
532	0.00	0.65	0.00	0.76	0.11	0.43	0.06	0.42	11.61	137.13	17.99	68.58
533	0.00	0.59	0.00	1.17	0.17	0.50	0.10	0.44	30.63	143.52	17.09	67.94
541	0.00	0.43	0.00	0.49	0.29	0.29	0.13	0.26	59.38	61.35	30.86	40.15
542	0.00	0.54	0.00	0.94	0.10	0.44	0.07	0.44	33.86	100.83	19.24	55.45
543	0.00	0.67	0.00	1.04	0.12	0.49	0.05	0.50	25.48	150.80	10.77	74.56
551	0.00	0.90	0.00	0.56	0.16	0.42	0.12	0.37	30.73	91.23	20.28	55.03
552	0.00	0.76	0.02	0.62	0.10	0.27	0.07	0.22	58.74	122.07	30.40	60.92
553	0.00	0.79	0.18	0.94	0.22	0.36	0.14	0.30	87.59	114.01	36.75	58.22

11

12 **Table S4:** Lookup values for condition indicator scaling - Land systems: Units: AGB
13 (Mg/Ha), SOC (Mg/Ha), EV (mm/yr), TBP (kg/Ha).

ID	AGB		SOC		EV 2010		EV 2020		TBP 2010		TBP 2020	
	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX
11	0.00	1.04	0.00	1.24	0.16	0.55	0.10	0.59	0.03	140.20	2.95	63.69
12	0.00	1.10	0.00	1.71	0.14	0.54	0.08	0.55	0.00	176.56	10.88	77.45
13	0.00	1.08	0.00	0.99	0.18	0.49	0.12	0.53	33.68	163.38	19.84	71.39
21	0.00	1.07	0.00	1.11	0.11	0.55	0.05	0.59	0.00	137.68	0.00	68.00
22	0.00	1.14	0.00	1.25	0.11	0.54	0.05	0.52	10.00	164.35	3.06	74.95
23	0.00	1.14	0.00	1.17	0.14	0.48	0.07	0.54	21.31	181.34	16.15	80.57
31	0.00	1.07	0.00	0.96	0.09	0.42	0.06	0.40	22.48	125.22	15.34	66.41
32	0.00	1.08	0.00	0.87	0.09	0.51	0.04	0.49	0.00	150.44	0.00	81.18
33	0.00	1.12	0.00	1.45	0.12	0.51	0.05	0.55	0.00	172.58	0.00	81.67
41	0.00	1.03	0.00	0.83	0.09	0.30	0.06	0.29	55.86	105.03	30.68	61.98
42	0.00	1.02	0.00	1.07	0.08	0.45	0.03	0.44	25.61	156.52	10.01	81.13
43	0.00	1.13	0.00	1.53	0.12	0.54	0.03	0.51	0.00	168.51	0.00	81.95
51	0.00	1.07	0.00	1.01	0.09	0.42	0.06	0.50	30.73	120.54	20.71	65.87
52	0.00	1.12	0.02	1.26	0.06	0.46	0.03	0.46	55.13	156.58	25.87	81.13
53	0.00	1.11	0.10	1.48	0.09	0.46	0.05	0.53	51.76	176.09	9.01	80.92

14

15 Appendix B: Python script for condition index 16 calculations by ecosystem type.

```
17 import subprocess
18 import os
19 import pandas as pd
20 # Configuration
21 saga_cmd = r"C:\Users\xavier\Desktop\saga-8.5.1_x64\saga-8.5.1_x64\saga_cmd.exe"
22 input_raster = r"C:\IOGA_Post_Stage\2.Ecosystem
23 Condition\Operations_Indicators\2020_Ops_Frst\2020_AGB\AGB_2020_10m.sgrd"
24 shapefile_base = r"C:\IOGA_Post_Stage\2.Ecosystem
25 Condition\Operations_Indicators\2020_Ops_Frst\Polygons"
26 output_dir = r"C:\IOGA_Post_Stage\2.Ecosystem
27 Condition\Operations_Indicators\2020_Ops_Frst\2020_AGB\Output"
28 lookup_table = r"C:\IOGA_Post_Stage\2.Ecosystem
29 Condition\Operations_Indicators\Lookups\AGB_MIN_MAX.csv"
30
31 # Shapefile ids for forest ecosystems
32 shapefile_ids = ['211', '212', '213', '221', '222', '223',
33                 '231', '232', '233', '241', '242', '243',
34                 '251', '252', '253']
35 # Read lookup table
36 df_lookup = pd.read_csv(lookup_table)
37 lookup_dict = df_lookup.set_index('ID').to_dict('index')
38 # Create output directory if it doesn't exist
39 os.makedirs(output_dir, exist_ok=True)
40 # Process each shapefile
41 for shape_id in shapefile_ids:
42     shapefile = os.path.join(shapefile_base, f"{shape_id}.shp")
43
44     if not os.path.exists(shapefile):
45         print(f"Warning: Shapefile {shapefile} not found, skipping...")
46         continue
47
48     # Step 1: Clip raster with shapefile using grid_tools 31 - Clip Grids
49     clipped_raster = os.path.join(output_dir, f"clipped_{shape_id}.sgrd")
50
51     clip_cmd = [
52         saga_cmd, "grid_tools", "31", # Clip Grids
53         "-GRIDS", input_raster, # Changed from -INPUT to -GRIDS
54         "-POLYGONS", shapefile,
55         "-CLIPPED", clipped_raster,
56         "-EXTENT", "3" # 3 = polygon extent
57     ]
58     print(f"Clipping raster with {shape_id}...")
59     result = subprocess.run(clip_cmd, capture_output=True, text=True)
```

```

60     if result.returncode != 0:
61         print(f"Error clipping {shape_id}: {result.stderr}")
62         continue
63
64     # Step 2: Rescale using grid calculator
65     shape_id_int = int(shape_id)
66     if shape_id_int not in lookup_dict:
67         print(f"Warning: No lookup values found for ID {shape_id_int}, skipping rescaling...")
68         continue
69
70     MIN = lookup_dict[shape_id_int]['MIN']
71     MAX = lookup_dict[shape_id_int]['MAX']
72
73     output_raster = os.path.join(output_dir, f"rescaled_{shape_id}.sgrd")
74
75     # Grid calculator formula: (V - Vl)/(Vh - Vl)
76     formula = f"(g1 - {MIN}) / ({MAX} - {MIN})"
77
78     grid_calc_cmd = [
79         saga_cmd, "grid_calculus", "1",
80         "-GRIDS", clipped_raster,
81         "-FORMULA", formula,
82         "-RESULT", output_raster,
83         "-NAME", f"Rescaled_{shape_id}"
84     ]
85     print(f"Rescaling {shape_id} with formula: {formula}...")
86     result = subprocess.run(grid_calc_cmd, capture_output=True, text=True)
87     if result.returncode != 0:
88         print(f"Error rescaling {shape_id}: {result.stderr}")
89         continue
90
91     # Optional: Export to GeoTIFF
92     output_tif = os.path.join(output_dir, f"rescaled_{shape_id}.tif")
93     export_cmd = [
94         saga_cmd, "io_gdal", "2",
95         "-GRIDS", output_raster,
96         "-FILE", output_tif,
97         "-FORMAT", "GTiff"
98     ]
99     print(f"Exporting {shape_id} to GeoTIFF...")
100    result = subprocess.run(export_cmd, capture_output=True, text=True)
101    if result.returncode != 0:
102        print(f"Error exporting {shape_id}: {result.stderr}")
103
104    print(f"Successfully processed {shape_id}")
105    print("Processing complete!")
106

```

107 Appendix C: Sensitivity analysis

108 Sensitivity analysis was carried out to assess the influence of indicator weight on the
109 composite index as shown in Figure S1. This was constrained to land condition results
110 as they represent the entire island of Mauritius, and for the year 2020. The LAND_2020
111 curve shows the land index as computed above and serves as reference curve, with
112 administrative units (Municipal and Village Council Areas – MVCA, the second
113 administrative level after districts) ranked in descending order of index value to ease
114 visualisation. The remaining curves represent index values when one indicator is given a
115 weight of 0.05 and the remaining five indicators are given an equal weight of 0.19 (the
116 sum of weights amounting to 1), in the same unit order as the reference curve. Figure S1
117 (a), (b) and (c) present two curves and the reference curve for clarity, while Figure S1(d)
118 shows all six sensitivity curves on the same chart. Curves below the reference indicate
119 that the corresponding indicators (of which the weight was reduced) have a positive
120 causal influence on the index – i.e. the decreasing weight of an indicator decreases the
121 index overall. Conversely, those rising above the reference curve express a negative
122 causal influence on the index. Dominant effects and nuances thereof are described in
123 Table S5 for each indicator, and may inform expert deliberations on assigning indicator
124 weights, a process which may be undertaken towards specific policy priorities and
125 goals.

127

128

129

130 **Figure S1:** Effect of individual indicators on the index, by MVCA (x-axis) – 2020 values.

131 Source: Authors' elaboration.

132 Reducing the weight of individual indicators had distinct effects on the land index
 133 across administrative units, which underscores the parsimony of selected indicators as
 134 depicted by Figure S1 (d). In other words, the index responds differently to each
 135 indicator. For the purposes of this thesis, upper and lower bound condition indices were
 136 not produced, as this would simply equate to different indicator weighing schemes for
 137 which biophysical interpretations would be difficult.

138 **Table S5:** Indicator impact on condition index. Source: Authors' elaboration.

Indicators positively influencing condition	
EV	Reducing the EV weight generally results in a decrease of index values across the island, though more markedly so for units containing river catchments, and those of the central plateau characterised by low-slope and large agricultural areas (Figure S1a.)
SOC	Reducing SOC weight causes the index to decrease, albeit with high variability due to the heterogeneous distribution of built-up areas (low SOC) and a concentration of high SOC in the central plateau of the island. (Figure S1a.)
TBP	The reduction of TBP weight leads to the most pronounced decrease of index values across the island, to a lesser degree for areas where elevated biomass stocks are highly productive. (Figure S1c.)
Indicators negatively influencing condition	

HNVI	As most of the island is characterised by low HNVI value, the overall condition index increases when HNVI is given a low coefficient, save for few units containing large areas of high biodiversity value. (Figure S1b.)
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Indicators of varying effects

AGB	Reducing the weight of AGB causes the condition index to increase or decrease according to, respectively, the low or high biomass stock of individual units. This curve however remains the closest to the reference. (Figure S1b.)
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Continuity	Reducing the weight of continuity causes sharp area-by-area variations above and below the reference, as units exhibit large differences in continuity across the island. In degraded areas, which are generally highly urbanised and densely connected by transport infrastructure, reducing the weight of continuity generally increases the condition index. In some areas towards the left of the chart, it is evident that high continuity contributes to high condition, which is expressed by sharp index decrease when the continuity weight is reduced. (Figure S1c.)
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140 Appendix D: Inclusion of IAS coverage as compositional 141 indicator

142 The presence and distribution of invasive species, if accurately mapped, can be
143 integrated in the index as a compositional indicator (Keith et al., 2020; Czúcz et al.,
144 2021). For demonstration purposes, this was undertaken for the year 2020 as described
145 in section 3.2.1 (Table 2), resulting in revised land index values for the concerned
146 administrative units, i.e. primarily those containing forests. The overall impact on land
147 index is shown in Figure S2, revealing that over a third of MVCAs are concerned. It must
148 be noted that the index range was shifted upward due to the amended indicator weights
149 and the introduction of the IAP indicator. This is further explained by its directionality,
150 where a value of 1 denotes the absence of IAP, and conversely a value of 0 denotes
151 presence, so that presence of IAP has a negative impact on the index. This highlights the
152 potential variability of the index range according to the chosen indicators, their
153 individual ranges, and chosen rules for unitless indicators such as binary presence-
154 absence values.

155

156 **Figure S2:** Reference land condition index (CI_REF) and IAP-adjusted index (CI_IAP) per
 157 MVCA in descending order for (a) all MVCAs and (b) higher condition MVCAs typically
 158 containing forests and affected by IAP. Source: Authors' elaboration.

159 As IAPs primarily affect forests, a representation of results for forest ecosystems is
 160 relevant to concerned authorities, namely the Forestry Service and the NPCS. Figure S3
 161 therefore displays total forest and IAP coverage extents, reference index values for
 162 forests (as per section 1.1.) and IAP-adjusted index by ecosystem type. Notably, the
 163 considered IAPs appear to occur primarily in wet regions, supporting the ecosystem
 164 classification proposed in the paper. *Ravenala madagascariensis* is, however, but one
 165 of several invasive species which have proliferated in Mauritian forests (Florens et al.,
 166 2016; Koerner, Chadwick & Tebbs, 2022). Further research is, therefore, needed to

167 validate these results and map the extent of dominant species for more accurate
168 ecosystem condition evaluations.

169
170 **Figure S3:** Extent of IAP coverage by Forest ET and impact on the index. Source: Authors'
171 elaboration.

172

173 **Appendix E: Data used for 2050 scenarios and maps.**

174 **Table E1:** Sources for georeferenced urban development plans. Source: Author’s
 175 elaboration.

Project Name	Type	Masterplan source
Anahita Beau Champ	Smart City	https://blog.anahitamauriti.us.com/property/anahita-beau-champ-sustainable-development/
Avalon	Golf Estate	https://golf-villaslux.com/
Azuri	Smart City	https://www.azuri.mu/masterplan-azuri/
Beau Plan	Smart City	https://beauplan.mu/about/
Bagatelle (Moka)	Smart City	https://www.moka.mu/en/masterplan/
Cote d’Or	Smart City	https://coirec.mu/coirec/index.php/cote-dor-project/
Courchamps (Moka)	Smart City	https://www.moka.mu/en/masterplan/
Ferney	Smart City	https://ferney.mu/real-estate/farm-side-residences-south-coast-mauriti.us/
Harmonie	Golf Estate	https://www.harmonie.mu/en
Helvetia (Moka)	Smart City	https://www.moka.mu/en/masterplan/
L’Avenir (Moka)	Smart City	https://www.moka.mu/en/masterplan/
Curzon	Smart City	https://www.curzonmauriti.us.com/curzon-smart-city
Medine	Smart City	https://www.medineproperty.com/
Mont Choisy	Smart City	https://www.visitmontchoisy.com/mont-choisy-master-plan/
Montebello	Smart City	https://montebello.mu/masterplan/
Mon Tresor	Smart City	https://architectsstudiolt.d.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/02-ASL-MASTERPLAN-230116.pdf
Saint Felix	Smart City	Unavailable at the time of writing. See below image.
Savannah (Moka)	Smart City	https://savannah.mu/en/masterplan/
Telfair (Moka)	Smart City	https://www.moka.mu/en/masterplan/
Tribeca	Smart City	https://tribecacentral.com/location.html
Vivea (Moka)	Smart City	https://www.moka.mu/en/masterplan/

176

177

178 Saint Felix Masterplan, obtained online in 2024, taken offline in 2025 (URL no longer
 179 available).

180 The two LC scenarios for 2050 respectively feature additional urbanisation (SC1), both
 181 urbanisation and reforestation of grass and shrubland (SC2), and additional
 182 conversions in both scenarios including completed golf courses and green spaces
 183 (gardens) in new smart cities, the latter being classified as grass & shrubs. Figure (a)
 184 shows new urban areas (red), bringing the total coverage from 254km² in 2020 to
 185 317km² in 2050, primarily replacing land-in-development and croplands. In SC2, tree
 186 cover has replaced 61km² of 2020 grass & shrub areas (Figure (b)).

187

188 **Figure E1:** (a) 2050 SC1 change compared to 2020, (b) 2050 SC2 change compared to
 189 2020, (c) reference 2020 LC. District boundaries and names indicated throughout.

190 Source: Author's elaboration.